

Bonding and debonding on demand with temperature and light responsive supramolecular polymers

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ABSTRACT: Due to their low melt viscosity, competitive adhesive properties, and the stimuli-responsive nature of supramolecular interactions, various supramolecular polymers have recently been investigated as adhesives with on-demand (de)bonding capability. We here report on the adhesive properties of a series of hydrogen-bonded supramolecular polymer networks based on a telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (PEB) terminated with isophthalic acid (IPA) groups and a series of bifunctional pyridines (Py). These supramolecular polymers microphase segregate into an IPA-Py rich hard phase and an amorphous low-glass-transition PEB phase, and their properties depend on the nature of the pyridine-carrying monomer. Rheological measurements show that the polymers disassemble into low-viscosity melts when heated above the melting or glass transition temperature of the hard phase. Lap joints bonded with the polymers displayed a shear strength of up to 1.3 MPa, and debonding is possible in less than 10 s upon heating or exposure to UV-light; to enable rapid light-induced (de)bonding, a light-heat converter was introduced. Cyclic bonding/debonding experiments revealed that the shear strength remained unchanged over five cycles and demonstrate that the process is very robust.

ToC FIGURE

1. Introduction

Adhesives that can be debonded on demand by means of a remote stimulus are useful in a variety of applications including the repair of structural components,^[1-4] the temporary fixation of pieces for manufacturing purposes,^[5-6] the recycling of bonded parts,^[7-8] and the removal of wound care dressings.^[9-10] Depending on the application, thermoplastic hot melt adhesives or pressure-sensitive adhesives are employed, and several schemes that allow for debonding have been developed.^[11-13] Hot-melt adhesives display stronger bonds than pressure sensitive adhesives,^[14-16] but their high melt viscosity renders processing of hot-melt adhesives intricate, leads to long debonding times, and makes the removal of the adhesive after debonding difficult.^[17-19]

Several approaches to achieve debonding on demand have been introduced in recent years, including the combination of thermoset adhesives with shape memory polymers that reduce the bonding area on demand and in turn facilitate debonding,^[20-23] the use of reversible covalent chemistry to thermally depolymerize cross-linked adhesives,^[24] the use of magnetically responsive fillers that locally increase the temperature as a response to an electromagnetic field,^[25] and the development of polymers that change their mechanical properties in response to changes in temperature or pH,^[26-28] among others.^[29-30] Another recently proposed general concept is the utilization of supramolecular polymers, as these materials present an attractive combination of adequate mechanical and adhesive properties and fairly low melt viscosity,^[31-32] which roots in the stimuli-responsive nature of dynamic, non-covalent interactions through which the monomeric units of supramolecular polymers are held together.^[33] Unlike “traditional” covalent polymers, supramolecular polymers are formed by monomers that are linked through hydrogen bonds, metal complexes, host-guest interactions, or other non-covalent, dynamic interactions.^[33-34] The strength of these interactions depends on external parameters such as the temperature, the pH or the presence of chemicals, and the bulk properties

of supramolecular polymers (*e.g.*, modulus, adhesive strength) can thus be modified by exposure to such stimuli.^[35-36]

The body of work dedicated to the investigation of supramolecular polymer-based adhesives has grown rapidly since the early works of Stupp and coworkers on π - π stacking mediated adhesion,^[37] and of Long and co-workers on hydrogen-bonded polyacrylates.^[38] In the meantime, several types of supramolecular interactions have been explored in the context of debonding on demand.^[31] A majority of studies focused on the use of hydrogen-bonded systems, many of which involved Meijer and Sijbesma's ureidopyrimidinone (UPy) motif.^[39-45] While the intrinsically reversible nature of supramolecular adhesives has been investigated in many studies,^[32, 46-51] it was not until recently that researchers started to investigate such polymers as adhesives with on demand debonding capability in a systematic manner. Several studies addressed the debonding on demand of supramolecular adhesives based on hydrogen bonding,^[52-53] as well as host-guest interactions^[49-50, 54-55] by means of simple heating, but also via exposure to molecules that disassemble the binding motifs or irradiation with UV-light.^[30, 42-43, 45, 56-57]

We here report on the rheological behavior and adhesive properties of supramolecular polymers assembled with the help of the hydrogen-bonding motif isophthalic acid-pyridine (IPA-Py).^[57-59] Despite the fact that the IPA-Py binding motif exhibits a very low association constant ($K_a \sim 500 \text{ M}^{-1}$),^[60] hydrogen-bonded supramolecular polymer networks assembled from a telechelic poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (PEB) based building block that was end-functionalized with isophthalic acid groups and bipyridines display mechanical properties that are comparable to those of similar polymers made with much stronger-binding motifs.^[42] This behavior is related to microphase segregation into a low-glass-transition PEB phase and a binding-motif-rich hard phase that physical cross-links the network and also stabilizes the binding. In the light of these properties, the fact that their modular design allows one to readily change the debonding temperature, and that the low binding constant should translate into very efficient debonding in response to external stimuli, we studied the adhesive behavior and the

rheological properties of a family of supramolecular polymers based on an IPA-functionalized PEB telechelic and seven different bipyridines,^[59] and investigated the debonding and rebonding characteristics upon exposure to heat or UV-light.

2. Experimental Section

2.1. Materials.

P1 was synthesized as previously reported.^[59] **P1** cannot be analyzed by size exclusion chromatography (SEC) as it is only soluble in common organic solvents (such as THF or CHCl₃) upon addition of a few drops of trifluoroacetic acid (TFA). Its number-average molecular weight ($M_n = 4500 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) was thus determined by ¹H-NMR end-group integration, while the dispersity (D) can be assumed to mirror the one of the parent PEB telechelic (*ca.* 1.07), from which it was synthesized.^[58] Bipyridines **a-g** were synthesized as previously reported, and polymer films **P1a-P1g** were processed following a reported procedure.^[59] 2-Tert-butyl-6-(5-chloro-2H-benzotriazole-2-yl)-4-methylphenol (Tinuvin 326, Ciba Specialty Chemicals, Inc.) and CDCl₃ (99.8% deuterated, Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc.) were used as received.

2.2. Characterization and methods.

2.2.1. ¹H-NMR Spectroscopy.

¹H-NMR spectra were acquired in CDCl₃ and CDCl₃/TFA on a Bruker AVANCE III 400 spectrometer operated at 400 MHz. The chemical shifts (δ) are quoted in parts per million (ppm) relative to tetramethylsilane; however, the solvent signal of CDCl₃ was used as internal standard ($\delta = 7.26 \text{ ppm}$). The relaxation time D1 was set to 5 seconds and the number of scans to 32.

2.2.2. Preparation of Tinuvin 326-containing supramolecular polymer films.

P1b, **P1e** and **P1g** were dissolved in CHCl_3 and Tinuvin 326 was added (0.75 wt% for **P1b**, 0.25 wt% for **P1e**, and 1 wt% for **P1g**). The solutions were cast onto glass slides, the solvent was evaporated under ambient conditions in a well-ventilated hood, and samples were subsequently dried under reduced pressure in an oven at 80 °C for 2 h. The materials this obtained were processed into films with a thickness of 100 μm by compressing-molding as described in Section 2.2.4.

2.2.3. Rheology.

Rheological experiments were conducted on a TA Instruments AR-G2 rheometer with a 40 mm parallel plate setup in oscillatory mode. A Peltier element was used for temperature control. Precut films of *ca.* 300 μm thickness were used. An average mass of 1.5 g of a given supramolecular polymer **P1b**, **P1e**, **P1g** or **P1f** was placed in between two Teflon[®] sheets and this sandwich was placed between two metal plates of 15 x 15 x 0.2 cm that had been pre-heated to the polymer's respective melting temperature, and then a weight of 3 kg was placed on top for 2 min to obtain films of *ca.* 300 μm thickness and a diameter of at least 4 cm. Prior to each rheology measurement, samples were trimmed between the plates at a temperature of 10 - 15 °C above the melting transition (**P1b**: 90 °C, **P1e**: 70 °C, **P1g**: 140 °C, **P1f**: does not show melting transition, the sample was heated to 90 °C) at a normal force of *ca.* 0.5 N. The samples were subsequently cooled to their respective crystallization temperature (**P1b**: 47 °C, **P1e**: 38 °C, **P1g**: 120 °C, **P1f**: does not have T_c , it was cooled to ambient temperature, *ca.* 25 °C) and the temperature was held constant for 1 h to allow the samples to crystallize. Frequency sweep experiments were conducted over a frequency range of $\omega = 0.05 - 600 \text{ rad}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ and 0.5% strain at temperatures between 30 and 120 °C; the temperature was increased in 15 °C increments. For some samples, an additional frequency sweep was performed at the melting temperature determined by DSC. After the final frequency sweep experiment, samples were once more

crystallized at the respective crystallization temperature for 1 h prior to the temperature-dependent viscosity measurements conducted between 30 and 130 °C (30-150 °C for **P1g**) at 10 rad·s⁻¹ and 0.5% strain.

2.2.4. Compression molding.

Compression molding was used to shape supramolecular polymer films for the preparation of the lap joints. Films were prepared by compression molding neat **P1a-P1g** or Tinuvin 326-containing **P1b**, **P1e** and **P1g** between Teflon[®] sheets in a Carver[®] CE Press at 20 °C below the T_m of each polymer with the help of a 100 µm thick aluminum foil spacer, to control the supramolecular polymer film thickness. 5 Tons of pressure were applied for 3 min and the films thus made were removed from the press and cooled to room temperature between Teflon[®] sheets.

2.2.5. Single lap joint tests.

Single lap joint tests were performed with stainless steel as well as glass slides as substrates in a ZWICK/Roell Z010 tensile tester equipped with a 200 N load cell and mechanical gripping clamps. A strain rate of 1 mm·min⁻¹ was applied at ambient temperature. Both the glass and stainless steel slides were custom made to have a width of 10 mm. The glass slides were cut from commercially available glass slides with a diamond tip while the stainless steel slides were laser cut at the workshop of the University of Fribourg. The stainless steel lap joints were prepared as follows. A well-defined amount of sample (1 cm² piece of a 100 µm thin film made by compression molding, *vide supra*) was placed between the stainless steel substrates, which were overlapped to create a bond area of 1 cm². The assemblies were heated to ($T > T_m$) on a Kofler bench, gently pressed together, and then immediately transferred to an oven that had been pre-heated to the T_c of the supramolecular polymer used (**P1a**: 42 °C; **P1b**: 47 °C; **P1c** and **P1d**: 60 °C; **P1e**: 38 °C; **P1g**: 120 °C; **P1f** is amorphous, no thermal treatment was applied to this sample) where they were left for 12 h before performing the lap joint tests. As previously

reported, this thermal treatment maximizes the crystallization of the IPA-Py motifs (hard phase) and ensures the reproducibility of the results.^[59] The glass lap joints were prepared as the stainless steel lap joints with three differences, *i.e.*, i) supramolecular polymers containing Tinuvin 326 were used, ii) UV-light (Hönle Bluepoint 4 Ecocure UV lamp equipped with an optical fiber and a 320 – 390 nm filter, $I = 950 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, 120 s), instead of direct heat, was used to melt the supramolecular polymers, and iii) the lap joints were not subjected to a thermal treatment before the shear tests. The lap joints were clamped in the tensile tester using an initial clamping force and the shear stress was recorded as a function of the strain until failure of the lap joint. The initial clamping force recorded for each sample was subsequently subtracted from the shear stress data obtained for each sample to obtain the real shear strength values shown in Table 1 and discussed in this article. 10 Lap joints were prepared for each material. After the single lap joint tests, the failed lap joints were rebonded to investigate the recyclability of these adhesives. Rebonding was achieved either thermally or with UV-light by bringing back into contact the two slides of the failed lap joint (no additional adhesive was applied) and then applying heat or UV-light following the same procedure as described for the freshly prepared lap joints.

2.2.6. Debonding-on-demand experiments.

Thermally triggered on demand debonding experiments were carried out on stainless steel lap joints bonded with **P1b**, **P1e** and **P1g**. In brief, lap joints were prepared as described above and a constant standard force corresponding to 20% of the shear strength of the corresponding sample was applied. The lap joints were then exposed to a well-defined temperature ($T = \sim 20 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ above the T_m of each supramolecular polymer, measured with a thermometer placed next to the heat-exposed lap joint's area) with the help of a heat gun and the shear stress was recorded over time until the lap joint failed. The UV-light triggered debonding experiments were performed following the same procedure using glass slides as substrate and polymer samples

with or without Tinuvin 326. UV-light was applied using a Hönle Bluepoint 4 Ecocure UV lamp equipped with an optical fiber and a 320-390 nm filter and an intensity of 900-950 mW·cm⁻². Three individual tests per sample were performed.

2.2.7. Surface temperature measurements.

An Optris PI Connect infrared camera (model PI 160, Roth AG, Switzerland) was used to record surface temperature profiles of a glass slide and of supramolecular polymers upon UV-light irradiation. The surface temperature of a glass slide was recorded by focusing the IR camera on the top surface while the opposite surface was exposed to the UV-light source listed above. The surface temperature of films of supramolecular polymers was recorded by placing the films on a glass slide, irradiating the polymer films *through* the glass slide with UV-light and focusing the IR camera directly on the polymer film surface.

2.2.8. UV-vis absorption measurements.

Solid-state UV-vis spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-2401 PC spectrophotometer. CHCl₃ solutions of the supramolecular polymers and of Tinuvin 326 were spin-coated on quartz slides, and the resulting thin films were analyzed.

3. Results and Discussion

The supramolecular polymers **P1a-P1g** were prepared by combining the IPA-functionalized PEB telechelic polymer **P1** ($M_n = 4500 \text{ g} \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$) with bipyridines **a-g** (**Figure 1a**), as previously reported.^[59] In these materials, the amorphous PEB backbone phase segregates from the crystalline IPA-Py motifs (except in the case of **P1f**, which is amorphous), and this results in semicrystalline materials with a low glass transition temperature (T_g) of around -50 °C and a melting temperature (T_m) that depends on the bipyridine component and ranges from 55 to 130 °C (**Figure 1b**). The concentration of the IPA-Py motifs in these supramolecular polymers

impacts their association and also the solid-state morphology, and has thus a significant influence on the mechanical (and adhesive) properties.^[61] Therefore, the molecular weight of the PEB segment is an important parameter. For PEB telechelics we^[62] and others^[63-64] have found that building blocks with an M_n of 3000 – 8000 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ afford supramolecular polymers that exhibit thermoplastic elastomer characteristics, and their properties change from rubber-like to viscous liquid as they are heated above the T_m (**Figure 1c**).^[59] This behavior is caused by the disassembly of the supramolecular polymers into monomeric units when the crystalline phase – which physically cross-links the polymers and also locks the hydrogen-bonded IPA-Py motifs in place – melts. We hypothesized that such a sharp property change, a low melt viscosity, and the fact that the disassembly temperature can be easily tuned through the bipyridine component, would render these materials good candidates for (de)bonding on demand applications.

In order to study the rheological behavior of these materials, we measured the temperature-dependent viscosity of **P1b**, **P1e**, **P1f**, and **P1g** as representative samples, using a rheometer equipped with parallel plates in oscillatory mode. **Figure 2** shows the evolution of the complex viscosity of these four samples as a function of temperature. The semicrystalline samples (**P1b**, **P1e** and **P1g**) display viscosities between $4.4\cdot 10^4$ and $1.9\cdot 10^5$ $\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$ at 30 °C, show a relatively stable plateau, and a step-like decrease of their viscosity around their respective T_m . On the other hand, and in agreement with its amorphous nature, **P1f** exhibits the lowest viscosity at 30 °C ($2.6\cdot 10^4$ $\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$) and instead of a step-like viscosity drop, a more gradual decrease is observed as the temperature is increased. The very different behavior of **P1b** and **P1f**, whose only difference is a methyl side-group in the structure of the bipyridine component, clearly demonstrates the stark influence that crystallization of the hard phase exerts on the physical properties of these polymers; while the semicrystalline **P1b** shows higher complex viscosities and a rubbery plateau below the melting temperature, the lack of a rubbery plateau in the case of **P1f** is in agreement with the absence of crystalline domains. However, at temperatures above

the melting of **P1b**, both materials exhibit very similar complex viscosities, indicating similar structural features in the melted states. All samples show very low complex viscosities in the melt, ranging from 2 Pa·s at 130 °C for **P1e** to 23 Pa·s for **P1g** at 150°C.

To further investigate the effect of temperature on the structure and assembly of these samples, we carried out oscillatory frequency sweeps. Dynamic measurements of the four samples were performed below, at and above their respective T_m (**Figure 3**). In the case of the semicrystalline samples, the storage modulus dominates the loss modulus over the whole frequency range below T_m , reflecting that the typical behavior of cross-linked polymers. A clear property change takes place as the temperature is increased above T_m , where their behavior is small-molecule-like, *i.e.* typical flow behavior is observed.^[65] Thus, the data support the conclusion that the sharp viscosity decrease observed above the T_m is due to the melting of the hard phase and disassembly of the supramolecular polymers into monomeric or oligomeric species and validates the expectation that these materials will rapidly lose their adhesive properties when heated above that transition temperature.

Single lap joint tests using stainless steel substrates were carried out to investigate the adhesive properties of **P1a-P1g**. Thus, well-defined amounts of the various materials (1 cm² pieces of 100 μm thin films) were placed between two steel plates and the assembly was heated to $T > T_m$ while applying gentle pressure (see Experimental Section for details). The lap joints were subsequently transferred to an oven that had been pre-heated to the T_c of the respective polymer and annealed at this temperature for 12 h before performing the lap joint tests. This thermal treatment maximizes the crystallization of the IPA-Py motifs and thus eliminates differences that may arise from incomplete crystallization. **Figure 4** shows representative plots of the shear stress as a function of strain for all samples (note that these are not corrected for the pre-strain applied and should therefore not be directly compared) and the (pre-strain corrected) data are collected in **Table 1** (see **Figure S3** for all shear stress plots of samples **P1a-P1g**). The results evidence significant differences among the different supramolecular

adhesives, which can to some extent be related to the nature of the bipyridine and the resulting hard phase; interestingly, however, they all show a mixture of adhesive and cohesive failure mechanisms, although the adhesive failure mode appears to prevail. With the exception of the lap joint bonded with the amorphous **P1f**, which displays the lowest shear strength (0.15 ± 0.06 MPa) and shows no yield strain but a creep-like behavior, all shear tests show a steep increase of the shear stress, shear strengths between 0.31 ± 0.16 MPa and 1.28 ± 0.15 MPa, and a characteristic yield strain above which either the lap joints fail or a significant stress drop can be observed. The highly ordered microstructures of **P1e** and **P1g** (lamellar and hexagonal morphologies, respectively)^[59] appear to have a positive impact on their adhesive properties and the lap joints bonded with these materials display the highest shear strengths, 0.85 ± 0.12 MPa and 1.28 ± 0.15 MPa, respectively. Interestingly, these two samples respectively match or even exceed the shear strength observed for lap joints made with a similar material based on UPy-UPy interactions (0.9 MPa),^[42] which suggests that the supramolecular unit's binding strength is not necessarily the most important parameter that governs the adhesive strength. **Figure 5** shows a comparison of the measured shear strength and the previously reported storage modulus^[59] of all materials and serves to illustrate the tunability of this two-component system. As expected, lap joints made with the amorphous **P1f** display a lower shear strength than the other, semicrystalline, materials. Among the latter, there is no clear correlation between the storage modulus and the shear strength, which is consistent with the predominantly adhesive failure mode that was observed and indicates that the bond strength is not a priori limited by the polymers' intrinsic mechanical properties.

To investigate the possibility to rebond lap joints formed with the supramolecular polymers under investigation, lap shear tests were conducted and the failed lap joints were thermally rebonded following the same procedure as described above. The rebonded lap joints were subjected to a second shear test, and this procedure was repeated for up to five bonding/debonding cycles. With the exception of the lap joints bonded with **P1c** and **P1e**, the

shear strength was observed to increase between 26% and 87% after five cycles (**Table 1** and **Supporting Table S2**), perhaps due to better wetting of the substrates taking place through the multiple recycling steps and perhaps also some thermally triggered cross-linking. However, the data show that **P1a-P1g** can *a priori* be recycled several times with similar or even improved shear strength.

We also explored the possibility of binding two glass substrates with **P1e** using UV-light, exploiting that the non-radiative decay of the optically excited states can be utilized to convert light into heat.^[66] In order to maximize this effect in the weakly absorbing **P1a-P1g**, we blended these polymers, as previously reported,^[42-43, 56] with the light-to-heat converter 2-*tert*-butyl-6-(5-chloro-2*H*-benzotriazole-2-yl)-4-methylphenol (Tinuvin 326). **P1e** was thus mixed with 0.25 wt% of Tinuvin 326 and a film of this blend was placed between two glass slides with an overlap area of 1 cm² as described above. UV-light ($\lambda = 320 - 390$ nm, 950 mW·cm⁻²) was subsequently applied for 120 s to melt **P1e** and form a single lap joint. A shear test revealed a cohesive failure mode and a six times lower shear strength (0.13 ± 0.07 MPa) than was observed for the thermally bonded stainless steel lap joint (0.85 ± 0.12 MPa). Both differences can be ascribed to the fact that - unlike the heat-bonded lap joints - the optically bonded samples were not annealed, and therefore the polymer was not crystallized to the fullest extent possible. Nevertheless, this experiment demonstrates clearly that UV-light can be used to bond objects with these materials, which presents practical advantages.^[67-68] The failed lap joint could be easily rebonded by putting the two glass slides back into contact and applying UV-light for 120 s before repeating the shear test. After five such bonding/debonding cycles (**Supporting Figure S7** and **Supporting Table S3**), the shear strength (0.19 ± 0.02 MPa) was not significantly changed, which shows the reversibility of this adhesive material also using UV-light as processing stimulus.

The debonding-on-demand behavior of these materials was explored using heat and UV-light as stimuli. Thanks to the narrow molecular weight distribution of **P1** (the *D* of the PEB

precursor was *ca.* 1.07, see Materials Section), these materials present very-well defined microstructures and crystalline phases. As a result, the transition from solid state to flow behavior occurs in a very narrow temperature range and rapid debonding should be observed upon exposure to the adequate stimulus. For the heat-triggered debonding experiments, stainless steel lap joints bound with **P1b**, **P1e** and **P1g** were prepared as described for the single lap joint tests. The samples were subjected to 20% of their shear strength (*cf.* **Table 1**) and then controlled heat was applied with a heat gun (see Experimental Section for details). **Figure 6a** shows the evolution of stress, measured as the standard force, with time. For each sample, two experiments are shown; a control experiment in which no heat was applied and a debonding test in which heat was applied after time lapse of 30 s. While the three controls do not show any stress variation on time, all lap joints rapidly debond after heat application (**Table 2**). The lap joint bound with **P1g**, which has the highest T_m of the three supramolecular polymers, shows the longest debonding time (7.5 ± 1.5 s). On the other hand, the lap joint bound with **P1b** debonds in only 2.7 ± 1.3 s.

UV-light was subsequently used to trigger debonding of thermally-bonded lap joints prepared with glass slides following the same procedure as for the stainless steel lap joints. As in the previous experiment, the lap joints were subjected to 20% of their shear strength but, instead of direct heat, UV-light was applied with a light source ($\lambda = 320 - 390$ nm, $950 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). **Figure 6b** shows the evolution of stress for lap joints bonded with **P1b**, **P1e** and **P1g** in the absence (control experiment) and presence of UV-light irradiation. The lap joints bonded with **P1b** and **P1e** show a similar behavior as observed for the thermal debonding, however, the time required for debonding is much higher (*ca.* 80 s and 20 s, respectively, **Table 2**). The stress profile of the lap joint bonded with **P1g** on the other hand is the same in the control experiment and the UV-light triggered debonding test, *i.e.* no debonding occurs. These results are not surprising, as the optical extinction in the UV regime is fairly low (**Figure S4**). Indeed, surface temperature measurements with an IR camera revealed that their surface temperature increased to only 55 –

70 °C when irradiated for 60 s through a glass slide (**Supporting Figure S5**). We therefore blended **P1b**, **P1e** and **P1g** with a small amount (0.25 – 1.0 wt%) of the UV-light absorber Tinuvin 326 (**Supporting Figure S4 and S5**). Once mixed with the UV-light absorber, the surface temperature of the samples increased to 120 – 150 °C after the same irradiation time and under the same conditions (**Supporting Figure S5**). **Figure 6c** shows the debonding experiments carried out with the same samples now containing Tinuvin 326. The control lap joints did not debond within the studied time-frame, however, in contrast to the previous results, all samples debonded much rapidly once exposed to UV-light showing reaction times close to those observed with direct heat exposure in the order of 8 – 10 s (**Table 2**). The debonding times observed are much shorter than for the aforementioned UPy-based adhesive blended with Tinuvin 326, which under similar conditions required 30 s, arguably due to the lower binding constant of the IPA-Py motif that leads to a lower melt viscosity. It is thus possible to conclude that the adhesive strength of UPy based adhesives can be matched (or even increased) by supramolecular adhesives based on much weaker binding units which, also show a much faster response to external stimuli.

4. Conclusions

The two main advantages of supramolecular adhesives over thermoplastic hot melts are their enhanced processability and dynamic nature, which enable a rapid response to external stimuli for debonding-on-demand applications. The two-component supramolecular adhesives reported here show very low melt viscosity as a result of the very weak H-bonds they are based upon, but display reasonably high shear strength (towards stainless steel and glass) in the solid state, thanks to the buildup of a crystalline hard phase. However, the system shows relatively slow hard phase crystallization and a thermal pre-treatment is required to maximize adhesion. Frequency sweeps on selected samples below, around and over the melting temperature of the hard phase show that this temperature marks the transition between polymer-like and monomer-

like properties, and hence between the bonded and debonded states. The debonding-on-demand experiments reported here show that this transition can be readily induced by direct heat and by UV-light irradiation allowing for the rapid debonding of stainless steel and glass lap joints in less than 10 s. In addition, the dynamic nature of these materials allows for their recycling up to at least five bonding/debonding cycles. This family of supramolecular adhesives thus present several advantages over similar materials reported in the past including lower melt viscosity, faster response to external stimuli, and the possibility of tuning their transition temperature by simple component choice.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the authors.

Appendix/Nomenclature/Abbreviations

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References

- [1] V. R. Allies, W. D. Zimmermann (Henkel Loctite Corp), *DE2612546A1*, **1979**.
- [2] C. Kirsten, A. Ferencz, M. Hirthammer (Henkel AG and Co KGaA), *DE19904835A1*, **2000**.
- [3] K. W. Kreckel, N. Karim (3M Innovative Properties Company (US)), *WO 1992011333 A1*, **1992**.
- [4] W. A. Nijhuis *WO 2012143190 A1*, **2012**.
- [5] H.-J. Dittmers, J. Stock, D. Thorns *WO9412582A1*, **1994**.
- [6] I. Y. Han, H. G. Song, S. W. Park, H. Ji-Seok (Samsung Electronics Co Ltd), *US 20120234497A1*, **2012**.
- [7] M. D. Banea, L. F. M. da Silva, R. D. S. G. Campilho, C. Sato, *J. Adhesion* **2014**, *90*, 16.
- [8] Y. C. Lu, J. Broughton, P. Winfield, *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* **2014**, *50*, 119.
- [9] M. Adler, D. Kruh (M. Adler), *US 6063231 A*, **2000**.
- [10] K. A. Kasprzak (Dow Silicones Corp), *DE3028780A1*, **1983**.
- [11] W. Brockmann, P. L. Geiß, J. Klingen, B. Schröder, In *Adhesive Bonding: Materials, Applications and Technology*, (Eds.: W. Brockmann; P. L. Geiß; J. Klingen; B. Schröder), Wiley-VCH, 2009, pp 39-100.
- [12] X. Luo, K. E. Lauber, P. T. Mather, *Polymer* **2010**, *51*, 1169.
- [13] M. M. Sheridan, J. L. Bries, J. D. Malmer, A. A. Sherman, D. J. Kinning (3M Innovative Properties Company (US)), *US 6,569,521 B1* **2003**.
- [14] M. M. Feldstein, E. E. Dormidontova, A. R. Khokhlov, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* **2015**, *42*, 79.
- [15] C. Creton, *MRS Bull.* **2011**, *28*, 434.
- [16] J. Courtois, I. Baroudi, N. Nouvel, E. Degrandi, S. Pensec, G. Ducouret, C. Chanéac, L. Bouteiller, C. Creton, *Adv. Funct. Mater.* **2010**, *20*, 1803.
- [17] A. J. Inglis, L. Nebhani, O. Altintas, F. G. Schmidt, C. Barner-Kowollik, *Macromolecules* **2010**, *43*, 5515.
- [18] A. Bakken, N. Boyle, B. Archambault, A. Hagen, N. Kosty, K. Fischer, R. Taleyarkhan, *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* **2016**, *71*, 66.
- [19] M. B. Saeed, M.-S. Zhan, *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* **2007**, *27*, 9.
- [20] T. Xie, X. C. Xiao, *Chem. Mater.* **2008**, *20*, 2866.
- [21] R. Wang, X. Xiao, T. Xie, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2010**, *31*, 295.
- [22] S. Kim, M. Sitti, T. Xie, X. Xiao, *Soft Matter* **2009**, *5*, 3689.
- [23] S. Reddy, E. Arzt, A. del Campo, *Adv. Mater.* **2007**, *19*, 3833.
- [24] J. H. Aubert, *J. Adhesion* **2003**, *79*, 609.
- [25] E. Verna, I. Cannavaro, V. Brunella, E. G. Koricho, G. Belingardi, D. Roncato, B. Martorana, V. Lambertini, V. A. Neamtu, R. Ciobanu, *Int. J. Adhes. Adhes.* **2013**, *46*, 21.
- [26] M. K. Nguyen, C. T. Huynh, D. S. Lee, *Polymer* **2009**, *50*, 5205.
- [27] K. Liou, K. C. Khemani, F. Wudl, *Macromolecules* **1991**, *24*, 2217.
- [28] G. Sudre, L. Olanier, Y. Tran, D. Hourdet, C. Creton, *Soft Matter* **2012**, *8*, 8184.
- [29] C. Heinzmann, *Doctor rerum naturalium*, University of Fribourg, Fribourg, Switzerland, November 25th **2015**.
- [30] D. K. Hohl, C. Weder, *Adv. Opt. Mater.* **2019**, 1900230.
- [31] C. Heinzmann, C. Weder, L. M. de Espinosa, *Chem. Soc. Rev.* **2016**, *45*, 342.
- [32] Q. Zhang, C.-Y. Shi, D.-H. Qu, Y.-T. Long, B. L. Feringa, H. Tian, *Sci. Adv.* **2018**, *4*.
- [33] L. Yang, X. Tan, Z. Wang, X. Zhang, *Chem. Rev.* **2015**, *115*, 7196.
- [34] T. F. de Greef, E. W. Meijer, *Nature* **2008**, *453*, 171.
- [35] R. J. Wojtecki, M. A. Meador, S. J. Rowan, *Nat. Mater.* **2011**, *10*, 14.
- [36] A. Hashizume, A. Harada, In *Supramolecular polymer chemistry*, First ed., (Ed.: A. Harada), John Wiley & Sons, 2012, pp 231-267.
- [37] S. I. Stupp, V. V. LeBonheur, K. Walker, L. S. Li, K. E. Huggins, M. Keser, A. Amstutz, *Science* **1997**, *276*, 384.
- [38] K. Yamauchi, J. R. Lizotte, T. E. Long, *Macromolecules* **2003**, *36*, 1083.
- [39] F. H. Beijer, R. P. Sijbesma, H. Kooijman, A. L. Spek, E. W. Meijer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **1998**, *120*, 6761.

- [40] S. H. M. Sontjens, R. P. Sijbesma, M. H. P. van Genderen, E. W. Meijer, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **2000**, *122*, 7487.
- [41] G. M. L. van Gemert, J. W. Peeters, S. H. M. Söntjens, H. M. Janssen, A. W. Bosman, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2012**, *213*, 234.
- [42] C. Heinzmann, S. Coulibaly, A. Roulin, G. L. Fiore, C. Weder, *ACS Appl. Mater. Inter.* **2014**, *6*, 4713.
- [43] C. Heinzmann, U. Salz, N. Moszner, G. L. Fiore, C. Weder, *ACS Appl. Mater. Inter.* **2015**, *7*, 13395.
- [44] P. Y. W. Dankers, M. C. Harmsen, L. A. Brouwer, M. J. A. Van Luyn, E. W. Meijer, *Nat. Mater.* **2005**, *4*, 568.
- [45] D. W. Balkenende, C. A. Monnier, G. L. Fiore, C. Weder, *Nat. Commun.* **2016**, *7*, 10995.
- [46] A. Feula, X. Tang, I. Giannakopoulos, A. M. Chippindale, I. W. Hamley, F. Greco, C. Paul Buckley, C. R. Siviour, W. Hayes, *Chem. Sci.* **2016**, *7*, 4291.
- [47] Y. Zhao, Y. Wu, L. Wang, M. Zhang, X. Chen, M. Liu, J. Fan, J. Liu, F. Zhou, Z. Wang, *Nat. Commun.* **2017**, *8*.
- [48] O. Roling, L. Stricker, J. Voskuhl, S. Lamping, B. J. Ravoo, *Chem. Commun.* **2016**, *52*, 1964.
- [49] Y. Ahn, Y. Jang, N. Selvapalam, G. Yun, K. Kim, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed. Engl.* **2013**, *52*, 3140.
- [50] Y. Takashima, T. Sahara, T. Sekine, T. Kakuta, M. Nakahata, M. Otsubo, Y. Kobayashi, A. Harada, *Macromol. Rapid Commun.* **2014**, *35*, 1646.
- [51] N. Ishikawa, M. Furutani, K. Arimitsu, *ACS Macro Lett.* **2015**, *4*, 741.
- [52] S. A. Fouquay, D. Goubard (Bostik S.A. (Paris, FR)), *US 20100193127A1*, **2010**.
- [53] R. Wang, T. Xie, *Langmuir* **2010**, *26*, 2999.
- [54] M. Cheng, F. Shi, J. Li, Z. Lin, C. Jiang, M. Xiao, L. Zhang, W. Yang, T. Nishi, *Adv. Mater.* **2014**, *26*, 3009.
- [55] T. Nakamura, Y. Takashima, A. Hashidzume, H. Yamaguchi, A. Harada, *Nat. Commun.* **2014**, *5*, 4622.
- [56] C. Heinzmann, I. Lamparth, K. Rist, N. Moszner, G. L. Fiore, C. Weder, *Macromolecules* **2015**, *48*, 8128.
- [57] D. W. R. Balkenende, R. A. Olson, S. Balog, C. Weder, L. M. de Espinosa, *Macromolecules* **2016**, *49*, 7877.
- [58] L. Montero de Espinosa, S. Balog, C. Weder, *ACS Macro Lett.* **2014**, *3*, 540.
- [59] A.-C. Ferahian, S. Balog, E. Oveisi, C. Weder, L. Montero de Espinosa, *Macromolecules* **2019**, *52*, 2164.
- [60] J. Y. Lee, P. C. Painter, M. M. Coleman, *Macromolecules* **1988**, *21*, 954.
- [61] L. de Lucca Freitas, M. M. Jacobi, G. Gonçalves, R. Stadler, *Macromolecules* **1998**, *31*, 3379.
- [62] A. Sehlinger, N. Bartnick, I. Gunkel, M. A. R. Meier, L. Montero de Espinosa, *Macromol. Chem. Phys.* **2017**, *218*, 1700302.
- [63] B. J. B. Folmer, R. P. Sijbesma, R. M. Versteegen, J. A. J. van der Rijt, E. W. Meijer, *Adv. Mater.* **2000**, *12*, 874.
- [64] H. Kautz, D. J. M. van Beek, R. P. Sijbesma, E. W. Meijer, *Macromolecules* **2006**, *39*, 4265.
- [65] C. Chassenieux, L. Bouteiller, In *Supramolecular Chemistry: From Molecules to Nanomaterials* Vol. 2, (Eds.: P. A. Gale; J. W. Steed), John Wiley & Sons, 2012, pp 517-528.
- [66] M. Burnworth, L. Tang, J. R. Kumpfer, A. J. Duncan, F. L. Beyer, G. L. Fiore, S. J. Rowan, C. Weder, *Nature* **2011**, *472*, 334.
- [67] M. H. Shuangwu, D. L. W. Pang, S. Nathapong, P. Marimuthu Presented at *2008 10th Electronics Packaging Technology Conference*, (9-12 December **2008**).
- [68] W. Brockmann, P. L. Geiß, J. Klingen, B. Schröder, In *Adhesive Bonding: Materials, Applications and Technology*, (Eds.: W. Brockmann; P. L. Geiß; J. Klingen; B. Schröder), Wiley-VCH, 2009, pp 205-369.

Figure 1. a) Chemical structure of the supramolecular polymers used in this study, which are based on the hydrogen bonding between IPA-terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) **P1** and bipyridines **a-f** or terpyridine **g**, and optionally the UV-light absorber Tinuvin 326. b) Table showing the melting temperature (T_m) of the hard phase of supramolecular polymers **P1a-g**.^[59] c) Schematic representation of the transition between the solid and melt state of supramolecular polymers **P1a-g** upon heating or exposure to UV-light, which is the basis for the changes in adhesive properties reported in this study.

Figure 2. Temperature-dependent complex viscosity of the amorphous **P1f** and crystallized **P1b**, **P1e**, **P1g**; measurements were carried out at 10 rad·s⁻¹ and 0.5% strain.

Figure 3. Rheological data acquired in frequency sweep experiments ($\omega = 0.05\text{-}600 \text{ rad}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$, 0.5% strain) of a) **P1b** at 60, 78 and 90 °C, b) **P1f** at 30, 45 and 75 °C, c) **P1e** at 45, 55 and 60 °C and d) **P1g** at 120, 130 and 145 °C. G' corresponds to the elastic modulus and G'' to the viscous modulus.

Figure 4. Representative single lap joint shear tests of metal substrates heat-bonded with supramolecular polymers **P1a-P1g**. Shown are stress-strain curves performed on a tensile tester. Note that the lap joints were mounted in the tensile tester with an initial clamping force that is not shown and which has to be subtracted from the shear stresses shown in this Figure to reflect the actual shear stress values displayed in Table 1. Representative examples of six to ten individual measurements for each sample are shown.

Table 1. Shear strength of single lap joints of metal substrates bonded with supramolecular polymers **P1a-P1g**. The values of each sample are averages of 6 to 10 independent tests.

Sample	Shear strength [MPa]	Shear strength 5 th cycle [Mpa]
P1a	0.31 ± 0.16	0.47 ± 0.16
P1b	0.54 ± 0.14	0.68 ± 0.10
P1c	0.56 ± 0.13	0.48 ± 0.13
P1d	0.35 ± 0.17	0.60 ± 0.10
P1e	0.85 ± 0.12	0.74 ± 0.20
P1f	0.15 ± 0.06	0.28 ± 0.06
P1g	1.28 ± 0.15	1.77 ± 0.05

Figure 5. Comparison of the storage moduli (E') of the supramolecular polymers **P1a-P1g** (established by dynamic mechanical analysis and the shear strength of single lap joints of stainless steel substrates bonded with the same materials. E' values are reproduced from Ref.^[59])

Figure 6. Debonding experiments with single lap joints that had been thermally bonded with supramolecular polymers **P1b**, **P1e** and **P1g**. The lap joints were placed in a tensile tester, a constant force was applied (13 N for **P1b**, 18 N for **P1e** and 30 N for **P1g**), and the force was monitored as function of time. Two tests are shown for each lap joint: Either no stimulus was applied (control) or a stimulus (heat or UV-light) was applied at $t = 30$ seconds (marked by an arrow). a) Thermal debonding of metal lap joints by increasing the temperature up to 20 °C above the T_m of the corresponding supramolecular polymer. b) Debonding of glass lap joints using UV-light ($\lambda = 320\text{-}390$ nm, $950\text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$). c) Debonding of glass lap joints using UV-

light as in b) but in this case the glass lap joints were bonded with supramolecular polymers blended with a small amount of the UV-light absorber Tinuvin 326 (**P1b** + 0.75 wt%, **P1e** + 0.25 wt% and **P1g** + 1 wt%). The graphs show representative curves from three individual tests per sample.

Table 2. Debonding times observed for lap joints bonded with supramolecular polymers **P1b**, **P1e**, **P1g** upon application of heat or UV-light as stimuli. The lap joints were subjected to 20% of their shear strength during the debonding on demand experiments. The content of Tinuvin 326 in the corresponding samples was **P1b** (0.75 wt%), **P1e** (0.25 wt%) and **P1g** (1 wt%).

Sample	Time [s]		
	Heat	UV-light Neat polymer	UV-light Polymer + Tinuvin 326
P1b	2.7 ± 1.3	82.2 ± 5.9	10.3 ± 1.3
P1e	4.1 ± 2.3	20.7 ± 2.6	8.5 ± 0.1
P1g	7.5 ± 1.5	n.a.	9.3 ± 0.1

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Hydrogen-bonded supramolecular polymers (SPs) for bonding and debonding-on-demand adhesives are presented. Despite the fact that the isophthalic acid-pyridine motif shows a low association constant, the two-component SPs display attractive adhesive characteristics and enable fast debonding on demand.

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Bonding and debonding on demand with temperature and light responsive supramolecular polymers

ToC figure

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Supporting Information

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Bonding and debonding on demand with temperature and light responsive supramolecular polymers

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Figure S1. ^1H NMR spectrum of the isophthalic acid terminated poly(ethylene-*co*-butylene) (P1, 4500 $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) used in this study.

Figure S2. Schematic representation of the procedures used to characterize the adhesive properties of supramolecular polymers **P1a-P1g** by means of single lap joints. a) Procedure for bonding two slides with **P1a-P1g** to prepare single lap joints using heat or UV-light to melt the adhesive as described above. b) Schematic representation of the failure of a single lap joint during a shear test. c) Schematic representation of debonding-on-demand test using direct heat or UV-light as stimulus. d) Schematic representation of the rebonding of failed lap joints after a shear test or debonding-on-demand experiment.

Table S1. Previously reported thermal (DSC values) and mechanical (DMA values) data of the supramolecular polymers used in this study.^[59]

	T_c [°C]	T_g [°C]	T_m [°C]	E' at 25 °C [MPa]
P1a	42	-55	56	10.5 ± 1.6
P1b	47	-53	78	7.2 ± 2.8
P1c	60	-52	70	9.4 ± 1.5
P1d	60	-50	72	5.2 ± 1.2
P1e	38	-52	55	27.7 ± 2.0
P1f	n.a.	-52	n.a.	1.3 ± 0.3
P1g	120	-51	130	6.4 ± 1.9

Table S2. Shear strength values obtained from single lap joint tests with stainless steel lap joints bonded with supramolecular polymers **P1a-P1g**. The values labelled as “1st cycle” are those obtained from freshly prepared lap joints. The values labelled as “2-5 cycle” correspond to the shear strengths obtained from four subsequent recycling cycles in which the failed lap joints were rebonded and re-tested. Errors are standard deviation.

Shear Strength [MPa]							
	P1a	P1b	P1c	P1d	P1e	P1f	P1g
1 st cycle	0.31 ± 0.16	0.54 ± 0.14	0.56 ± 0.13	0.35 ± 0.17	0.85 ± 0.12	0.15 ± 0.06	1.28 ± 0.15
2 nd cycle	0.37 ± 0.08	0.58 ± 0.04	0.57 ± 0.13	0.42 ± 0.12	0.83 ± 0.17	0.18 ± 0.06	1.58 ± 0.19
3 rd cycle	0.45 ± 0.11	0.63 ± 0.10	0.54 ± 0.11	0.47 ± 0.18	0.79 ± 0.19	0.33 ± 0.07	1.69 ± 0.18
4 th cycle	0.55 ± 0.19	0.63 ± 0.08	0.58 ± 0.10	0.53 ± 0.20	0.76 ± 0.24	0.31 ± 0.05	1.78 ± 0.05
5 th cycle	0.47 ± 0.16	0.68 ± 0.10	0.48 ± 0.13	0.60 ± 0.10	0.74 ± 0.20	0.28 ± 0.06	1.77 ± 0.05
Mean	0.45 ± 0.17	0.61 ± 0.10	0.55 ± 0.12	0.48 ± 0.17	0.80 ± 0.18	0.25 ± 0.09	1.62 ± 0.23

Figure S3. Shear stress vs. strain curves obtained on single lap joint tests with stainless steel lap joints heat-bonded with supramolecular polymers **P1a-P1g**. Note that the lap joints were mounted in the tensile tester with an initial clamping force. This force has to be subtracted from the values shown in the curves in this Figure to reflect the real shear stress values.

Figure S4. UV-vis absorbance spectra of films of neat polymer **P1**, the UV absorber Tinuvin 326, **P1b** and **P1b** + 0.75 wt% Tinuvin 326, **P1e** and **P1e** + 0.25 wt% Tinuvin 326, **P1g** and **P1g** + 1 wt% Tinuvin 326. All samples were analyzed as thin solid films that had been spin-coated onto a quartz slide from CHCl_3 solutions.

Figure S5. Surface temperature profiles measured with an IR camera of a) a glass slide, b) neat **P1b** and **P1b** + 0.75 wt% Tinuvin 326 placed on a glass slide, c) neat **P1e** and **P1e** + 0.25 wt% Tinuvin 326 placed on a glass slide, and d) neat **P1g** and **P1g** + 1 wt% Tinuvin 326 placed on a glass slide. The samples were irradiated through the glass slide with UV-light ($\lambda = 320\text{-}390$ nm, $950\text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$) for 60 s starting at $t = 10$ s.

Figure S6. Shear stress vs. strain curves obtained on single lap joint tests with glass lap joints bonded with **P1e** (containing 0.25 wt% Tinuvin 326) using UV-light ($\lambda = 320\text{-}390$, $950 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, 120 s). The lap joints failed between 0.43 mm and 1.62 mm strain. Note that the lap joints are fixed on the tensile tester with an initial clamping force. This force has to be subtracted from the maxima shown in the curves in this Figure to reflect the real shear stress values.

Figure S7. Recyclability study. Shear stress vs. strain curves obtained on single lap joint tests with glass lap joints bonded with **P1e** (containing 0.25 wt% Tinuvin 326) using UV-light ($\lambda = 320\text{-}390$, $950 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, 120 s). Representative curves (of 10 individual tests per sample) of five recycling cycles are shown. Note that the lap joints are fixed on the tensile tester with an initial clamping force. This force has to be subtracted from the maxima shown in this Figure to reflect the real shear stress values.

Table S3. Shear strength values obtained in five consecutive bonding/debonding cycles using glass lap joints bonded with **P1e** containing 0.25 wt% Tinuvin 326. Every cycle, the lap joints were bonded using UV-light irradiation ($\lambda = 320\text{-}390 \text{ nm}$, $950 \text{ mW}\cdot\text{cm}^{-2}$, 120 s) to melt **P1e**. The overlapping area of the lap joints was 1 cm^2 . See Experimental Section for the detailed procedure. The shear strengths shown for each sample are averages of the values obtained from 10 independent tests.

	Shear Strength [MPa]	Shear strength mean [MPa]
1 st cycle	0.13 ± 0.07	0.15 ± 0.05
2 nd cycle	0.13 ± 0.04	
3 rd cycle	0.14 ± 0.03	
4 th cycle	0.18 ± 0.04	
5 th cycle	0.19 ± 0.02	